

Effluent Management in Oil and Gas Extraction

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Abstract:

The oil and gas industry is characterized by petrochemical industrial wastewater known basically as effluent, which typically contains various organic and inorganic components, naturally present or added during oil and gas processes. Thus, proper management or treatment is needed for reuse, discharge, or final disposal requiring complexity of the wastewater composition needing stringent discharge procedures, standards requiring combinations of treatment methods.

Effluent being a complex mixture of different organic and inorganic compounds (mostly salts, minerals, gas and oils), is majorly generated during oil/gas production. The volume of effluent is increasing around the world, and as a consequence, its discharge to the environment is one of the global concerns. The various methods of effluent management have their own advantages and disadvantages when used for offshore or onshore units. However, comprehensive and deep-understanding of each issue can provide a guideline for better and more practical solutions to its management. In this work, various physical and chemical treatment methods are reviewed and the most effective recommended to proper effluent management that meets all international standard and enhances sustainability. In this study the Pre-treatment, treatment and post treatment approaches employed reduced the amount of impurities present in the effluent with varying pH of 7.2 and 7.8, COD of 30 and 60mg/L, BOD value of 45 and 54 respectively, TSS value of 80 and 60mg/L and TDS of 5200 and 4800.

Keywords: *oil industry, effluents, toxic substances, treatment methods, sustainability.*

Introduction

Nigerian oil was discovered in 1956, and the country's production commenced in the late 1950s. Oil exploration became available to international businesses in the ensuing ten years, and by that time, the oil industry had grown steadily to become a global behemoth, with a few exceptions owing to economic conditions. The Nigerian National Petroleum Company (NNPC)

was established in 1977. The state-owned company's objectives are to oversee and take part in the nation's oil industry. Nigeria now produces the majority of the oil in Africa. Nigeria is the world's eleventh-largest oil producer in 2020, with 18 operational pipelines and an estimated 1.8 million barrels of oil produced daily on average. Nearly 90% of Nigeria's export value and 9% of its GDP are

attributed to the petroleum industry (Doris Dokua Sasu, 2023).

Oil and Gas Extraction is the exploration and exploitation of petroleum and natural gas from wells. The industry generates wastewater from the water extracted from the geological formations and from chemicals used during exploration, well drilling and production of oil and gas. The oil and gas industry produces approximately 14 billion bbls of effluent annually (Rodriguez and Soeder, 2015). These waste water varies greatly in quantity and quality and in some cases the water can be a useful by-product or even a salable commodity. The majority of this effluent is currently managed by injecting it underground, where it can no longer be accessible or utilised. In some cases, the limitations of injection are clear, necessitating other strategies. Several states and stakeholders are debating whether it makes sense to keep wasting this water, especially in regions of the country where there is a shortage of water, and what efforts would be required to purify and replenish it for other uses. Effluent has always been considered a waste, but in recent times, the industry is beginning to consider this material as a potential profit stream. Whether waste or commodity, effluent has management implications that need to be kept in-line with each specific production project and region or it could adversely affect the life of the well, thereby leaving substantial recoverable reserves in the ground. It could also have tremendous adverse impact on the environment, the drainage and aquatic system and on the health of humans and animals (Lofrano *et al.*, 2016). Wastewater from industries principally involved in refining crude oil, producing fuels and lubricants, and producing petrochemical intermediates (Harry *et al.*, 1995) is known as petroleum wastewater and is a significant cause of aquatic pollution in the environment. According to Coelho *et al.* (2006), the quantity of petroleum effluent produced during processing is 0.4–1.6 times that of the treated crude oil. The amount of dissolved oxygen needed by bacteria for normal survival declines if crude effluent with a significant amount of organic matter is released onto water bodies. Unpleasant colors and scents are

produced in water in anaerobic processes by the byproducts of chemical and biological reactions. In order to lessen that, water's oxygen availability is crucial (Attiogbe *et al.*, 2007). Effluent water handling practices must be environmentally protective and the methodology used in treating it depends on the composition of produced water, location, quantity and the availability of resources (Judd, 2016).

Statement of Research Problem

The management of effluent in the oil and gas industry is both a herculean and risky task. Industrial waste water from this industry is a hazardous process but essential for successful operation of the industry. The sources of water pollution can be categorized as point source and non-point source. Waste water pollutants from oil and gas wells are classified as point sources. Polluted water originates from physical, biological or chemical change in water quality which adversely affects living organisms or makes the water unsuitable for the desired use. Thus the need to understand the most appropriate treatment technique for effluent in the oil and gas industry. It is notable that while water is used in numerous oil and gas industry activities, not all of them necessitate raw or treated water. While some leftover water from the oil and gas refinery can be recycled or reused repeatedly inside the same facility, a significant amount needs management.

Objective of the Research

Ascertain the most sustainable effluent treatment approach.

Literature Review

The generally accepted definition of effluent is that of the United States Environmental Protection Agency (2006) as wastewater - treated or untreated - that flows out of a treatment plant, sewer, or industrial outfall. Generally refers to wastes discharged into surface waters (Fogler and Gurmen, 2015) The Compact Oxford English Dictionary defines effluent as "liquid waste or sewage discharged into a river or the sea (Mason *et al.*, 2016).

Effluent in the artificial sense is in general considered to be water pollution, such as the outflow from a sewage treatment facility or the wastewater discharge from industrial facilities.

The extraction of petroleum-based substances, that is an intricate combination of naturally occurring substances named crude oil and natural gas, and the production of hydrocarbon effluent are significant challenges because of the rising worldwide need for energy, which is projected to increase by 44% over the course of the next two centuries (Aljuboury *et al.*, 2017).

The purity of crude affects what is found in refining effluent. According to the operational circumstances (Benyahia *et al.*, 2006), it changes. Non-hydrocarbon compounds are eliminated in the refinery, where the crude oil is separated into its constituent components and combined to create products that are beneficial. Because of this, refineries that process petroleum generate large amounts of effluent, such as crude oil water generated from and restored on the outside during the extraction of petroleum, which is challenging to cleanse naturally and frequently contains compounds that are resistant (Vendrame *et al.*, 2015).

The quality of the crude affects the effluent in refinery wastewater. It varies depending on the circumstances. Some of the treatment methods for effluent in the oil and gas industry include: Chemical techniques, physical techniques and biological techniques. The oil and gas industries produce both liquid and gaseous pollutants. Gaseous pollutants are easier to manage as liquid pollutants are more complicated.

Over time, the vast oil exploration in Nigeria's Niger Delta has resulted in a number of environmental problems. In addition to oil spills, inadequate treatment of wastewater at oil refineries and the effluents that are emitted are now another potential cause of pollution that the government and the general public have not given sufficient consideration to (Osin *et al.*, 2017). According to the processing facility layout, how it operates, and the kind of oil that is processed, petroleum effluent might vary significantly (Aljuboury *et al.*, 2017). Production processes such as vapor condensation, used

caustic, and process water are the sources of effluents. Additionally, effluents may be produced by a cooling tower, surface runoff, or treatment of spilt petroleum products. Treatment of effluent and other liquid pollutants can be done using the following techniques as divided into 5 (five) categories as below (Fakhru *et al.*, 2009; Brindle 1994; Kirk *et al.*, 2002; Van *et al.*, 1998; Glaze, Kang and Chapin,

Preparatory or preliminary treatment: to remove coarse suspended and floating matters, oil or grease; primary or physical treatment: to remove settle able and suspended solids; secondary or biological treatment: to remove organic solids through a biological process; tertiary or advanced treatment: to achieve additional removal of suspended solids, colloidal particles, nutrients, and refractory organics and further reduction of fecal coli. Use of nanotechnology has demonstrated its ability to remove persistent organic pollutants (POPs) or transform harmful components into environmentally beneficial derivatives, it has also been suggested as a potential upgrade to existing treatment approaches as reported by Osin *et al.*, (2017).

Sources of Waste Water in Oil and Gas Industry

The availability of water is crucial to the procedures used in the oil and gas sector. The intricacy of the process, plant size, oil type, and products and chemicals used for treatment are just a few of the variables that can affect how much water is needed. A significant amount of wastewater is created during the refining process, and this wastewater gets into close proximity with hydrocarbons, producing pollution by some hydro-soluble oil components. Waste water can be categorized into a number of major classes as a result (Eldos *et al.*, 2022).

Produced Water

The majority of oilfield wastewater generated during the oil extraction or deep well injection process is known as produced water. Total soluble solids (TSS), chemical oxygen demand (COD), total organic carbon (TOC), hydrocarbons, and heavy metals are the most

frequent pollutants found in generated water Al-Ghouti *et al.*, 2019; Dawoud *et al.*, 2021).

Desalter effluent

In an oil refinery, a desalter is often the initial step in the process when hot crude oil is washed with feed water and chemical additives to remove the salt. The desalter effluent is the water produced during the washing process that desalinates the crude oil. Total Suspended Solid (TSS), Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), hydrocarbons, ammonia, and sulfides are the most frequent pollutants in desalter water. whichever is the type of feed water in the desalter unit, the levels vary (Bines *et al.*, 2017).

Stripped sour water

In order to reduce the petroleum portion of the pressure, heat is used in a variety of refining operations as a diluent in catalysis cracking and additional procedures along with an extraction carrier in distilling. The aqueous phase formed when the heated air condenses is removed as sour water. Hydrocarbons comprising hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) and ammonia (NH₃) get absorbed into the sour water at levels that often require treatment due to this steam compresses with the presence of these substances (Coelho *et al.*, 2006). The pollutants that are frequently found in sour water are COD, phenols, cyanide, sulfides, and ammonia. The origin of sour water used to make stripped sour water has a significant impact on the makeup of that water (Bastos *et al.*, 2020).

Tank bottoms water

When crude oil is retrieved from wells, water and sediments are frequently encountered in the raw form. This is referred to as bottom water and sediment. The bottom sediment and water that collect when oil is kept in large tanks must be constantly removed to prevent accumulation and a reduction in storage capacity. Typically, the sludge in these bottom tanks is moved for separation or to the wastewater treatment facilities. Water from tank bottoms frequently contains impurities such COD, hydrocarbons, TSS, and sulfides. Given that water comes into touch with crude oil in its unprocessed form, it

frequently has high COD and organic contents (Hochberg *et al.*, 2022).

Spent caustic effluent

When acidic elements from hydrocarbon streams are removed, spent caustic is created. These acidic substances include phenol, cyanide, organic acids, residual H₂S, and CO₂. The most frequent pollutants found in used caustic are sulfides, phenols, cyanide, H₂S, and RSH (mercaptans). The composition of used caustic effluents varies depending on the production process (Rita *et al.*, 2022).

Quality of Effluents from Oil and Gas extraction

Diverse levels of harmful substances, which include inorganic and organic contaminants such as petroleum hydrocarbons and heavy metals, are present in petroleum effluents. The primary effluent variables used to assess the water quality are total dissolved solids (TDS), total suspended solids (TSS), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), chemical oxygen demand (COD), total petroleum hydrocarbons (TPH), oil and grease (O&G), total organic carbon (TOC), and total metals and ions including ammonia, nitrates, sulfides, and others. More precise criteria, including cadmium, lead, and mercury, as well as some organics, including benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylene (BTEX), and inorganics, including phosphates, chlorides, and other micropollutants are also used. Physical characteristics of effluents, including pH (acids, alkalis), turbidity, color, and odor, are occasionally utilized as a sign of the water quality (Haneen *et al.*, 2022).

pH

One of the crucial factors that directly impacts how treatable petroleum effluents are is pH. It also affects the leachability of heavy metals and the dispersion of other contaminants. The proteinaceous matter content and ammonia compound discharge of petroleum effluents are revealed by their pH level. When using wastewater for agriculture, the ideal pH range ranges from 6.5 and 8.4. The amount of some compounds in the environment can alter as a result of a slight pH variation. Anions become

more soluble in alkaline solutions, whereas cations become more soluble in acidic solutions (Qaseem *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, acidic effluents alter the composition of the microbial ecosystem by reducing diversity of bacteria and altering microbial population dynamics (Król *et al.*, 2020).

Total dissolved solids (TDS), electric conductivity (EC), and salinity

The total dissolved solids (TDS) in petroleum effluents includes both organic and inorganic salts. Electrical conductivity (EC) gauges a liquid's capacity to carry an electric charge, which is influenced by the quantity and potency of the dissolved ions. As a result, EC and TDS are connected and both serve as measures of salinity. Salinity is the salt in petroleum effluents, an inorganic substance that is representative of the TDS notion. Petroleum effluents typically have TDS concentrations of 1000–400,000 mg/L. Additionally, the salinity of petroleum effluents is substantially higher than that of saltwater, ranging from a few parts per thousand (ppt) to 300 ppt. High TDS indicates hard water, which causes scaling and fouling in the treatment system, reducing treatment effectiveness and driving up maintenance costs (Al-Ghouti *et al.*, 2019; Ahmad *et al.*, 2020).

Total suspended solids (TSS)

TSS stands for total suspended solids, which includes biological matter, sand, sediments, and other non-soluble particles in effluents. The streams and contaminants found in the petroleum effluents heavily influence the range of TSS in petroleum effluents. TSS levels in petroleum effluents typically vary from 5 mg/L to 5 800 mg/L (Hodges *et al.*, 2017).

Oil and grease (O&G)

The phrase "O&G parameter" with reference to petroleum effluents covers a wide spectrum of chemical substances including oils, waxes, and fats from petrochemical sources. The amount of dispersed O&G in petroleum effluents is a crucial criterion to consider when assessing the security and efficacy of the water. By covering plants and animals and smothering them through the reduction of oxygen, the release of

petroleum effluents with a high concentration of oil and grease can have a significant negative impact on the natural habitat and creatures. Petroleum effluent contains O&G values ranging from 40 mg/L to 9000 mg/L (Eljaiek-Urzola *et al.*, 2019).

Total organic carbon (TOC), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), and chemical oxygen demand (COD)

Any petroleum effluent's organic intensity may typically be determined in three ways: TOC, COD, and BOD. The organic matter from natural sources and hydrocarbons from petroleum is represented by TOC in petroleum effluents. Both dissolved and granular organic carbon are involved. Because it makes the effluent less homogeneous, high TSS can impact the validity of TOC. The COD stands for the amount of oxygen needed to oxidize all of the OM in the PWWs. COD refers to the amount of oxygen needed to break down both biodegradable and non-biodegradable materials. In other words, TOC measures the quantity of carbon attached to organic molecules, whereas COD measures the amount of organic compound that will be oxidized. As a result, TOC and COD have a direct proportional relationship. BOD is a measure of the oxygen needed for microorganisms to biologically break down the organic matter in effluent. With respect for the organic matter's biodegradability, the higher the biological contamination in the sample, the greater quantity of oxygen the organisms will require, the worse the condition of the effluents. BOD is an approximate indicator of organic contamination in the effluent.

But investigations by El-Naas *et al.*, (2017), Janson *et al.*, (2015) and Lahlou *et al.*, (2020) revealed that the COD concentration in various petroleum effluents was 64 mg/L, 5300 mg/L, and 1572 mg/L, respectively. According to Kusworo *et al.*, the COD and BOD ranges in petroleum effluents are, respectively, 750-1600 mg/L and 300-1000 mg/L. As they are directly related to the breakdown remediation by microbes, the values of BOD, COD, and TOC are crucial in establishing the effective treatment

technology. Microbial degradation is not a suitable treatment if the wastewater's BOD, COD, and TOC values are very low since the microorganisms' ability to grow in such an environment will be negatively impacted, as will the efficacy of the treatment plant as a whole. On the reverse side, an excessive amount of organic matter can raise the amount of microbial biomass, posing many treatment difficulties that lower the effluent quality, such as bio-clogging and odor (Zhenget al., 2013).

Metals

Numerous investigations found various metals in petroleum effluents, but at varying quantities. Large amounts of metals like lead (Pb), zinc (Zn), iron (Fe), manganese (Mn), and barium (Ba) can be found in petroleum effluents. Petroleum effluents contain trace levels of other elements like cadmium (Cd), nickel (Ni), copper (Cu), chromium (Cr), and mercury (Hg). Ba, Cd, Cu, Cr, Fe, Ni, and Mn are among the heavy metals present in generated water from petroleum products at concentrations of 60.51 ppb, 0.05 ppb, 0.62 ppb, 30.31 ppb, 4144 ppb, 7.08 ppb, and 268.3 ppb, accordingly (Khan, 2021 and Al-Kaabiet al., 2019).

Total petroleum hydrocarbons (TPH)

The term "total petroleum hydrocarbons" describes the total amount of hydrocarbons in PWWs, which mostly consist of carbon and hydrogen. Petroleum hydrocarbons in suspended and dissolved forms make up TPH. Saturated, unsaturated, and aromatics make up the three main divisions. TPH is a mixture of volatile and extractable petroleum hydrocarbons made up of phenols, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), methyl tertiary butyl ether (MTBE), and naphthalic acids. It also contains volatile aromatic hydrocarbons such as benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylenes (BTEX) (Uddinet al., 2021).

Materials and Methods

Two effluents samples were collected from a local petroleum refinery in Rivers State at different points and the samples were named

PE 1 and PE 2. The samples were made to undergo different pre treatment, treatment and post treatment processes before they were further tested for pH, total dissolved solids, total suspended solids, oil and grease, etc.

Pre Treatment method

Sedimentation

In this process, the effluent was allowed to stand still in a beaker and this happens naturally because gravity will pull the heavier sediments down to form a sludge layer. Sedimentation is a treatment process in which suspended particles, like flocs, sand and clay are removed from the wastewater while crude oil settles at the top of the waste water. The advantage of sedimentation is that it minimizes the need for coagulation and flocculation process (Chu et al. 2018).

Filtration

After sedimentation, filtration method was employed. The crude oil that settled at the top of the beaker was decanted and was allowed to pass through sand and other filters of different pore sizes to remove suspended solids. The grease found on the surface of the wastewater was also removed easily through this method.

Treatment

Chlorination

Chlorination provides destructive treatments of aqueous phenols present in the effluent. 35mL of 4% Solution of sodium hypochlorite was dissolved in 500mL of pre treated effluent and was allowed to stand for 30 minutes to allow disinfection and partial removal of phenolic compounds present in the pre treated effluents.

Post treatment

Determination of pH

A digital pH meter (Apera AI209 series PH20) was dipped in a buffer and then placed in the treated effluent for about 2 minutes to determine its pH.

Determination of Total Dissolved solids

Weight of an empty beaker (W_0) was taken and treated effluent water sample was added with the weight taken again (W). The beaker containing

the sample was heated to dryness to allow the water to evaporate. Once all the water is evaporated, the weight of beaker along with the residue was recorded again (W_f).

Weight of effluent treated water (W_{te}) = $W - W_o$

weight of residue = W_r (g) = W_r (mg) = $W_f - W_{te}$

weight of treated effluent water = W_{te} (g)

Volume of treated effluent water = V_{te} (L)

Since Density = Mass/Volume

Density of water 1g/cc

Volume of treated effluent water = Mass/Density of water

$V_{te} = W_{te}/1g$ or $W_{te}/1000mg/cc$

TDS = W_r/V_{te} in ppm.

Determination of total suspended solids

The treated effluent water sample was filtered using 1.5 micron filter and the residual contents was kept inside oven at 104°C and taken out after an hour. The dried weight of filter along with dried residue was taken. After subtracting the weight of filter in this weight, the suspended solids weight was found out by dividing the weight of suspended solids by volume of water in ppm.

Determination of Biochemical oxygen demand

The Biochemical or Biological oxygen demand was determined using the BLE-9100 dissolved oxygen meter. The electrode was dipped inside the treated water and reading was taken.

Determination of chemical oxygen demand

Results and Discussion

The treatment methods of the effluent are reliant on the effluents generated characteristics and this can give insights on the type of treatment options available to treat the effluents generated during oil exploration to reduce the hazardous effect of the effluent when discharged into water bodies. In this study, effluents generated was treated on laboratory scale and after treatment, several parameters were tested to check the level

of purity of the effluent. The effluents had a pH range of 7.2 to 7.8 as shown in the table 1 after treatment which is in conformity with the standard pH of waste water before they are discharged in to water bodies as stated by United States Environmental standard for effluent discharge.

Table 1. Various Parameters of the Two Different Points Of Effluents.

S/No	Parameters	PE1	PE2
1	pH	7.2	7.8
	Total suspended solid mg/L	80	60
	Total dissolved solid mg/L	5200	4800
	Oil and greese	NT	NT
	Chemical oxygen demand	30	60
	Biological oxygen demand	45	54

Note: No Traces

The total suspended and total dissolved solids had little variation ranging from 4800mg/L to 5200mg/L without any traces of oil and greese. The biological and chemical oxygen demand varied also but they are not suitable for or useful for aquatic life until further treatment technique is employed. Lahlou et al., 2020 reported that the COD of waste effluent from petroleum refinery was 10497mg/L while the BOD was 1034 for untreated effluents. Also in Tunisia, Karray et al., reported that effluents from petroleum refinery had 6444.93mg/L COD and 1310 BOD respectively. According to Environmental standards for effluent discharge as per the US EPA, the values of COD and BOD is 125mg/L and 15 respectively and from this study only the COD conforms with the standard.

Conclusion

This study revealed that effluents from oil and gas extraction could pose danger to aquatic and terrestrial life if not treated before they are discharged into water bodies or probably for

agricultural use because the varying results of parameters investigated showed that there are lots of impurities as well as toxic substances in the effluents before treatment and in view of this, more approaches should be employed to treat the effluents to reduce the level of impurities and toxic substances.

References

Ahmad, N. A., Goh, P. S., Yogarathinam, L. T., Zulkhairun, A. K., & Ismail, A. F. (2020). Current advances in membrane technologies for produced water desalination. *Desalination*, *493*, 114643.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2020.114643>

Al-Ghouti, M. A., Al-Kaabi, M. A., Ashfaq, M. Y., & Da'na, D. A. (2019). Produced water characteristics, treatment and reuse: A review. *Journal of Water Process Engineering*, *28*, 222-239.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2019.02.001>

Ali, N Bilal, M, Khan, A, Ali, F, Iqbal, H, M. (2020). Effective exploitation of anionic, contaminated soil remediation, *Science of Total Environment*, *704*(2020), 135391.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.135391>

Aljuboury, D. A. D. A., Palaniandy, P., Abdul Aziz, H. B., & Feroz, S. A. D. A. (2017). Treatment of petroleum wastewater by conventional and new technologies-A review. *Global Nest Journal*, *19*(3), 439-452.

<https://doi.org/10.30955/gnj.002239>

Al-Kaabi, M. A., Al-Ghouti, M. A., Ashfaq, M. Y., Ahmed, T., & Zouari, N. (2019). An integrated approach for produced water treatment using microemulsions modified activated carbon. *Journal of Water Process Engineering*, *31*, 100830.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2019.100830>

Attiogbe, F. K., Glover-Amengor, M., & Nyadziehe, K. T. (2007). Correlating biochemical and chemical oxygen demand of effluents—A case study of selected industries in Kumasi, Ghana. *West African Journal of Applied Ecology*, *11*(1).

<https://doi.org/10.4314/WAJAE.V11I1.45722>

Bastos, P. D., Santos, M. A., Carvalho, P. J., & Crespo, J. G. (2020). Reverse osmosis performance on stripped phenolic sour water treatment—A study on the effect of oil and grease and osmotic pressure. *Journal of environmental management*, *261*, 110229.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2020.110229>

Benyahia, F., Abdulkarim, M., Embaby, A., & Rao, M. (2006). *Refinery wastewater treatment: a true technological challenge*. In The Seventh Annual UAE University Research Conference. UAE University.

Bines, R. J., Sowell, M. W. & Woodhull, J. (2017). Desalter brine effluent pretreatment—an emerging process for heavy crude refiners. In *WEFTEC 2017*. Water Environment Federation.

Coelho, A., Castro, A. V., Dezotti, M., & Sant'Anna Jr, G. L. (2006). Treatment of petroleum refinery sourwater by advanced oxidation processes. *Journal of hazardous materials*, *137*(1), 178-184.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2006.01.051>

Coelho, J. P., Rosa, M., Pereira, E., Duarte, A., & Pardal, M. A. (2006). Pattern and annual rates of Scrobicularia plana mercury bioaccumulation in a human induced mercury gradient (Ria de Aveiro, Portugal). *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, *69*(3-4), 629-635.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2006.05.027>

Dawoud, H. D., Saleem, H., Alnuaimi, N. A., & Zaidi, S. J. (2021). Characterization and Treatment Technologies Applied for Produced Water in Qatar. *Water*, *13*, 3573.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/w13243573>

Eldos, H. I., Khan, M., Zouari, N., Saeed, S., & Al-Ghouti, M. A. (2022). Characterization and assessment of process water from oil and gas production: A case study of process wastewater in Qatar. *Case Studies in Chemical and Environmental Engineering*, *6*, 100210.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cscee.2022.100210>

Eljaiek-Urzola, M., Romero-Sierra, N., Segre-Cabarcas, L., Valdelamar-Martínez, D., & Quiñones-Bolaños, É. (2019). Oil and grease as a water quality index parameter for the

- conservation of marine biota. *Water*, 11(4), 856. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w11040856>
- El-Naas, M. H., Alhaija, M. A., & Al-Zuhair, S. (2017). Evaluation of an activated carbon packed bed for the adsorption of phenols from petroleum refinery wastewater. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 24, 7511-7520. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11356-017-8469-8>
- Karray, F., Fathi, A., Jemli, M., Mhiri, N., Loukil, S., Bouhdida, R., Mouha, N., & Sayadi, S. (2020). Pilot-scale petroleum refinery wastewaters treatment systems: Performance and microbial communities' analysis. *Process Safety and Environmental Protection*, 141. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psep.2020.05.022>
- Lahlou, F.Z., Mackey, H.R., McKay, G., Onwusogh, U. and Al-Ansari, T. (2020) Water Planning Framework for Alfalfa Fields Using Treated Wastewater Fertigation in Qatar: An Energy-Water-Food Nexus Approach. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 141, 106999. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compchemeng.2020.106999>
- Fogler, H. S., & Gurmen, M. N. (2015). 2008-Fogler, H. Scott and M. Nihat Gurmen-Elements of Chemical Reaction Engineering: Strategies for Creative Problem Solving. Retrieved from <https://www.simiode.org/resources/912>
- Hochberg, S. Y., Tansel, B., & Laha, S. (2022). Materials and energy recovery from oily sludges removed from crude oil storage tanks (tank bottoms): A review of technologies. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 305, 114428. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.114428>
- Hodges, A., Fica, Z., Wanlass, J., VanDarlin, J., & Sims, R. (2017). Nutrient and suspended solids removal from petrochemical wastewater via microalgal biofilm cultivation. *Chemosphere*, 174, 46-48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2017.01.107>
- Janson, A., Santos, A., Katebah, M., Hussain, A., Minier-Matar, J., Judd, S., & Adham, S. (2015). Assessing the biotreatability of produced water from a Qatari gas field. *SPE journal*, 20(05), 1113-1119. <https://doi.org/10.2118/173188-PA>
- Judd, S. J. (2016). The status of industrial and municipal effluent treatment with membrane bioreactor technology. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 305, 37-45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2015.08.141>
- Khan, S. H. (2021). Advanced approaches for heavy metals removal from industrial wastewater. In *New Trends in Removal of Heavy Metals from Industrial Wastewater* (pp. 403-440). Elsevier.
- Król, A., Mizerna, K., & Bożym, M. (2020). An assessment of pH-dependent release and mobility of heavy metals from metallurgical slag. *Journal of hazardous materials*, 384, 121502. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2019.121502>
- Lahlou, F. Z., Mackey, H. R., McKay, G., Onwusogh, U., & Al-Ansari, T. (2020). Water planning framework for alfalfa fields using treated wastewater fertigation in Qatar: An energy-water-food nexus approach. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 141, 106999. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compchemeng.2020.106999>
- Lofrano, G., Carotenuto, M., Libralato, G., Domingos, R. F., Markus, A., Dini, L., ... & Meric, S. (2016). Polymer functionalized nanocomposites for metals removal from water and wastewater: an overview. *Water research*, 92, 22-37. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2016.01.033>
- Mason, S. A., Garneau, D., Sutton, R., Chu, Y., Ehmann, K., Barnes, J., ... & Rogers, D. L. (2016). Microplastic pollution is widely detected in US municipal wastewater treatment plant effluent. *Environmental pollution*, 218, 1045-1054. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2016.08.056>
- Oil and Gas Extraction: Process & Standards (2023) *SafetyCulture*. Retrieved from <https://safetyculture.com/topics/oil-and-gas-extraction/>
- Osin, O.A., Yu, T. & Lin, S. (2017). Oil refinery wastewater treatment in the Niger Delta, Nigeria: current practices, challenges, and

recommendations. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 24, 22730–22740. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-017-0009-z>

Qasem, N. A., Mohammed, R. H., & Lawal, D. U. (2021). Removal of heavy metal ions from wastewater: A comprehensive and critical review. *Npj Clean Water*, 4(1), 36. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41545-021-00127-0>

Rita, A. I., Monteiro, A. L., Albuquerque, R. M., Santos, M., Ribeiro, J. C., Madeira, L. M., & Sanches, S. (2022). Unravelling the relation between processed crude oils and the composition of spent caustic effluents as well as the respective economic impact. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 421, 126629. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2021.126629>

Rodriguez, R. S., & Soeder, D. J. (2015). Evolving water management practices in shale oil & gas development. *Journal of Unconventional Oil and Gas Resources*, 10, 18-24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.juogr.2015.03.002>

Rusydi, A. F. (2018, February). Correlation between conductivity and total dissolved solid in

various type of water: A review. In *IOP conference series: earth and environmental science* (Vol. 118, p. 012019). IOP Publishing.

Uddin, S., Fowler, S. W., Saeed, T., Jupp, B., & Faizuddin, M. (2021). Petroleum hydrocarbon pollution in sediments from the Gulf and Omani waters: Status and review. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 173, 112913. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2021.112913>

Vendramel, S., Bassin, J. P., Dezotti, M., & Sant'Anna Jr, G. L. (2015). Treatment of petroleum refinery wastewater containing heavily polluting substances in an aerobic submerged fixed-bed reactor. *Environmental technology*, 36(16), 2052-2059. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09593330.2015.1019933>

Zheng, C., Zhao, L., Zhou, X., Fu, Z., & Li, A. (2013). Treatment technologies for organic wastewater. *Water treatment*, 11, 250-286. <https://doi.org/10.5772/52665>